

On the damped Pinney equation

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Abstract

In this note, we show that the damped Pinney equation, which finds many applications in nonlinear dynamics, can be transformed into a usual Pinney equation (*i.e.* without damping) but with a multiplicative coefficient for the non linear inverse-cubic term depending on the time variable. The transformation is of the same kind of change of variables as the one published by Laitone in 1957.

1 Introduction

The Pinney equation [1], published a long time ago in a famous and very short paper, has the form

$$f'' + p(t)f + \frac{c}{f^3} = 0 \quad (1)$$

with $f(t_0) = f_0 \neq 0$ and $f'(t_0) = f_1$, where $p(t)$ is a given function of time and c a non-zero constant. It was considered by Ermakov in 1880 [2] and is therefore referred to as the Ermakov-Pinney equation.

Equation (1) finds many applications in nonlinear dynamics [3], for instance as concerns classical and quantum oscillators [5], the stability of charged-particle motion in accelerators [6, 7], the derivation of the Feynman propagator [8], Bose-Einstein condensation in time-dependent traps, the phase-amplitude representation of the wavefunction in quantum mechanics, or the propagation of gravitational waves [9]. The previous list is of course non-exhaustive. The solution found by Pinney is

$$y''(t) = \pm \sqrt{u^2(t) - cv^2(t)} \quad (2)$$

where u and v are the solutions of the linear homogeneous equation

$$f'' + p(t)f = 0, \quad (3)$$

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for which $u(t_0) = f_0$, $u'(t_0) = f_1$ and $v(t_0) = 0$, $v'(t_0) = 1/f_0$. The + sign in Eq. (2) occurs if $f_1 > 0$ and the - sign if $f_1 < 0$. Since u and v form a fundamental set, in virtue of Liouville theorem, their Wronskian is equal to 1 $\forall t$, *i.e.* $u'(t)v(t) - u(t)v'(t) = 1$, $\forall t$. A substitution of $f(t) = \sqrt{u^2(t) - cv^2(t)}$ into Eq. (1) yields

$$f'' + p(t)f + \frac{c}{y^3} = -c \frac{[u'(t)v(t) - u(t)v'(t)]^2 - 1}{[u^2(t) - cv^2(t)]^{3/2}} = 0. \quad (4)$$

It is worth mentioning that for $c > 0$ some singular points are possible.

An interesting result was recently published by Korman [10], who noticed that, if $p(t)$ is a constant p_0 , Pinney's equation becomes linear for $z(t) = f^2(t)$. More precisely, he found

$$z'' + 4p_0z = 2 \left(f_1^2 + p_0f_0^2 - \frac{c}{f_0^2} \right), \quad (5)$$

with $z(0) = f_0^2$ and $z'(0) = 2f_0f_1$.

In section (2), we show, using a change of variables published by Laitone at the end of the fifties, that the damped Pinney equation can be transformed into an undamped Pinney equation with a multiplicative coefficient for the non linear inverse-cubic term depending on the time variable.

2 Case of damping

In the case of the damped Pinney equation (we consider here only a damping linear in velocity, such as the one occurring in the Stokes force in the study of viscous fluids), one has

$$f'' + p(t)f' + q(t)f + \frac{c}{f^3} = 0. \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) occurs for instance in quantum mechanical models including dissipation. In particular, the Kostin formulation of the non-conservative quantum time-dependent harmonic oscillator admits an exact Gaussian solution in terms of the solutions of an equation of that kind [11]. The Pauli equation for the Aharonov-Bohm effect with a time-dependent mass particle also involves such an equation [12].

In 1957, Laitone [13] published a change of variables making possible the transformation of a linear homogeneous damped equation into a linear undamped equation. Following his idea, let us set

$$\phi(t) = q(t) - \frac{p^2(t)}{4} - \frac{p'(t)}{2} \quad (7)$$

and define

$$g(t) = f(t) \exp \left[\int_0^t \frac{p(t')}{2} dt' \right], \quad (8)$$

which obeys therefore

$$g'' + \left(q(t) - \frac{p^2(t)}{4} - \frac{p'(t)}{2} \right) g + \frac{\chi(t)}{g^3} = 0, \quad (9)$$

i.e.

$$\boxed{g'' + \phi(t)g + \frac{\chi(t)}{g^3} = 0,} \quad (10)$$

where

$$\boxed{\chi(t) = c \exp \left[2 \int_0^t p(t') dt' \right].} \quad (11)$$

Therefore, we obtained an equation (9) which does not contain any damping term anymore and is of the standard Pinney form but with a non-linear term $1/g^3$ having a coefficient depending on the time variable, which is of course a major difference having implications on the general form of solutions.

3 Conclusion

In this note, we have shown that the damped Pinney equation, which finds many applications in nonlinear dynamics, can be transformed into a standard Pinney equation (*i.e.* without damping) but with a multiplicative coefficient for the non linear inverse-cubic term depending on the time variable. This constitutes of course an important difference, but such a property is worth pointing out since it may stimulate the derivation of solving methods.

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